

SUPPORT RESULT
JOURNALS**AUTHOR**

¹Toliboyev Dilshod
Muxammadiyevich
²Qo'shmanov Jamoliddin

¹Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston
Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali katta
o'qituvchisi.

²Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston
Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali
talabasi.

¹Toliboyev Dilshod
Mukhammadievich
²Kushmanov Jamoliddin

¹Senior lecturer of the Jizzakh branch of the
National University of Uzbekistan named
after Mirzo Ulugbek.

²Student of the Jizzakh branch of the
Uzbek national university named after
Mirzo Ulugbek.

¹Толібоев Дилшод
Мухаммадиевич
²Кушманов Джамалиддин

¹Старший преподаватель Джизакского
филиала Национального университета
Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.

²Студент Джизакского филиала
Национального университета
Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.

Email:toliboev@jbnuu.uz

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Mukhammadievich, Kushmanov
Jamoliddin.

Ekologik madaniyat va axloqiy-estetik tarbiyaning dialektik aloqadorligi

DIALECTICAL INVOLVEMENT OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE AND MORAL AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION

ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКАЯ СВЯЗЬ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И НРАВСТВЕННО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ

ANNOTATSIYA

Ekologik, axloqiy va estetik tarbiyani shakllantiradigan, mustahkamlaydigan va uyg'unlashtiradigan bir qator vositalar mavjud. Ular tabiatni axloqiy va estetik tarbiyaviy asoslari bilan uzviy bog'langan holda ijodiy yondashuv asosida qaror topadi. Tabiatga axloqiy yoki estetik munosabatda bo'lishlik darajasi insonlarning xatti-harakatlaridan, muomalalaridan ham sezilib turadi. Axloq inson qalbi xazinasidagi eng katta boylik hisoblanadi.

ANNOTATION

There are a number of tools that shape, strengthen and harmonize ecological, moral and aesthetic education. They decide on the basis of a creative approach, inextricably linked with the moral and aesthetic educational foundations of nature. The degree of moral or aesthetic attitude towards nature is also felt from the behavior, attitudes of people. Morality is the greatest wealth in the treasury of the human soul.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Существует ряд средств, которые формируют, укрепляют и гармонизируют экологическое, нравственное и эстетическое воспитание. Они решаются на основе творческого подхода, неразрывно связанного с нравственно-эстетическим воспитанием природы. Степень нравственного или эстетического отношения к природе также ощущается в поведении, поведении людей. Мораль-величайшее сокровище в сокровищнице человеческой души.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Ekologik tarbiya, axloqiy tarbiya, estetik tarbiya, ma'naviy meros, komil inson, ezgulik, komillik, ta'lim-tarbiya.

KEYWORDS

environmental education, moral education, aesthetic education, spiritual heritage, perfect person, goodness, perfection, education.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

экологическое воспитание, нравственное воспитание, эстетическое воспитание, духовное наследие, совершенный человек, добро, совершенство, воспитание.

INTRODUCTION

While part of the means of environmental, moral and aesthetic education are traditional means of upbringing, another part is modern means.

Today, the need to strengthen national moral and aesthetic education in young people is gaining importance in the strengthening of the process of informatization in society. Accordingly, the formation of a national ecological culture in young people constitutes a circle of urgent theoretical, methodological, practical tasks of moral-aesthetic education, scientific research on the place of spiritual heritage, the problems of the creative development of succession relations to it.

From the paradoxical principle of "the further we move away from history, the closer we get to it, the more we know it and the more we need to use it," we realize that the heritage of our oldest historical moral and aesthetic values is desperately needed for us today. In this regard, it is an important condition for solving problems and prospective tasks related to the study of the dialectical connection of the history of national ecological culture with moral and aesthetic education according to the requirements of the current environmental situation, organizing our practical activities accordingly, not repeating the mistakes made in the past.

MAIN PART

The formation of the ecological culture of the individual is a process directly related to the issues of upbringing. It is known that the main task of upbringing is to mature the human being. After all, the problem of man lies in all forms of upbringing, such as moral, aesthetic, educational, legal, economic, political. Each of them has its own influence on human education, based on its subject of research. And the ecological culture of a person is associated with his moral and aesthetic upbringing.

Moral education is a continuous process that ensures the maturation of a person as a person, it serves to enrich a person's qualities and rid him of vices. It is known that qualities are

considered the spiritual wealth of not only a person, but also Society. The increase in virtuous people in society affects the development of ecological culture, accelerates the development of knowledge in the field of Ecology.

Norms of morality and decency are formed on the basis of social relations, education. For this reason, the influence of sociability, upbringing in relation to naturalness in a person is strong. Education, the formation and development of social relations increasingly move the behavior of people, the relationship between them, away from the limits of natural needs and opportunities that are not connected with spirituality.

Therefore, moral education largely determines the following tasks:

- to ensure that people are committed to high moral ideals and understand the preservation of honor and dignity as high moral qualities;
- to cultivate morally pure, spiritually rich, conscientious, independent-minded people;
- the owner of a high moral culture, consists in strengthening the feelings of environmental awareness and manifestation of ecological culture.

Human maturation is multifaceted. His greatness, wisdom is primarily determined by the level of spiritual maturation. Only a person with mature spirituality tries to solve the problems of society and nature with his mind and intelligence, takes a rational approach to nature. Because a person achieves maturity under the influence of people around him. Already, Man is a part of nature and cannot stand aside from the problems in it.

The environmental and moral norms inherent in humans, its criteria, change under the influence of changes, intensification and vital needs of the problems of nature. Education, the formation and development of social relationships are increasingly moving away from the limits of natural needs and opportunities, provided that they do not associate the behavior

of people, the relationship between them with morality and elegance.

Abdullah Avloni defines morality as “Morality, which is a set of behaviors. And behavior is a form of manifestation of goodness or laziness in a certain person. Consequently, each behavior is the embodiment of goodness and Highness or selfishness of laziness. In this respect, they are divided into good and bad. But these do not appear in the person on their own. For their formation, a certain setting, upbringing is needed. Men are not born worse than they are born. They are made bad by certain conditions. So, everything is an attachment to upbringing. Education is either a matter of life, or of life, or of salvation, or of destruction, or of bliss, or of disaster” [3, 14].

In the younger generation, on the basis of new ideas, an understanding of an ecological culture based on moral-aesthetic education, a simple desire to build on it is not enough, but a certain spiritual level is also needed. The formation of this level is clearly Educational, the purpose of educational work is necessary to mobilize people not with adaptation to existing conditions and circumstances, but to the struggle for perspective, to activism. The goal of any upbringing will be broader in scope, more important in terms of importance.

The formation of the ecological culture of the younger generation is associated with its moral and aesthetic education. Zero moral and aesthetic education is one of the continuous processes that ensure the maturation of a person as a person. Beautiful qualities are something inherent in a person, not only his property. Good virtue is the wealth of society, has a universal meaning. People with positive qualities contribute to the beauty of nature, accelerate the development of environmental knowledge. The human child also simply does not come to this bright world. Philosopher scientist Erkin Yusupov believes: “it is easy to get confused about morality, but it is difficult to rise, it is easier to prevent it than to fight moral corruption. The

one who realizes that it is difficult to get back on his feet will try not to fall” [6, 82]

Man simply does not come to this bright world. In the words of the Hazrati Navoi, man comes to the world to achieve perfection. So the direction towards perfection means going directly towards spirituality. At this point, we consider it worthwhile to stop at the concept of “perfection”.

It is known that there are different interpretations of the concept of “perfection”. Religious teachings refer to right as the embodiment of perfection. Man's achievement of perfection is his interpretation of God. “Holy Islam” Imam Abu Homid al-Ghazzali writes in his work “Chemoi Saadat”: “man is a creature between an angel and an animal. The animal does not develop, since it has no maturation capacity. The Angel also does not develop, because it itself consists of pure divine light, because only humans have a sense of development, spiritual perfection.” [4, 172] it means that it is possible to educate a person, eliminate material - animal desires and increase the qualities of the divine-merciful. The perfect man is the truth of people, that is, the human being. As Najmiddin Komilov said, “a perfect man is an ideal, one who possesses all earthly and divine knowledge, his soul is attached to an absolute spirit, a noble one, his appearance is serene, his soul is full of noble feelings.” [5, 143]

Aziziddin Nasafiy writes with a description to a perfect person: “know that a perfect person is a person who is mature in Sharia and sectarianism and truth, and if you do not understand this phrase, say with another phrase: a perfect person is such a person that the following four things have matured in him: a good word, a good verb, good morality and” [5, 147]

Aziziddin Nasafi took two things as a basis as a sign of perfection. One of these is morality, the other is self – knowledge. Depending on whether these two bases existed or not, he classified people into three categories.

The first part is people - at least people who are not decorated with moral qualities and

do not know themselves. The latter are people who are at least decorated with moral qualities, but do not know themselves. The third category is people—people who are at least decorated with moral qualities and are self-aware.

Thus, a special moral rule of the perfect man is developed, which can be seen as the moral attitude of each person to nature to possess these qualities. It should also be noted that the concepts of good morality in the middle ages, about a perfect person, have a relative character. But no matter how the matter is put, ideas about a person with environmental, moral-aesthetic knowledge will have great socio-moral significance.

When a person does not get the right upbringing, his behavior harms nature. As noted by Hazrat Mirza Abdulqadir Bedil, “if the architect does not lay the original brick correctly, the wall will remain Crooked even if it reaches the stars”. It can be seen from this that the solution to all problems arising in nature comes true on the basis of selfless, honest work, cooperation, faith and faith of spiritually—morally mature people.

There are a number of tools that shape, strengthen and harmonize ecological, moral and aesthetic education. They decide on the basis of a creative approach, inextricably linked with the moral and aesthetic educational foundations of nature.

While part of the means of environmental, moral and aesthetic education are traditional means of upbringing, another part is modern means. Usually both types of tools are used. In the environmental moral education of the In particular, preschool age, with traditional upbringing through fairy tales and narratives, eco-modern upbringing through toys and games is successfully used; in this, the child is encouraged to look at the environment with a good eye, not dirty water, not plucking grass, not breaking tree branches with the help of games. In the environmental, moral and aesthetic education of Children, television, radio, computer, internet, Puppet Theater, Film Art play a large role.

On the ground of educational work lies goals that are associated with certain interests even in all periods. Enlightenment is a system of activities related to the study, promotion of the essence, significance of spirituality, the implementation of educational work. In any context, the spiritual maturation of society, the formation of the ecological culture of people, is realized through educational activities connected with certain goals.

As the unopened facets of nature are discovered, it brings new facets of spiritual, moral and aesthetic awareness and education. And not noticing the need to improve morality is a sign of a decline in environmental knowledge.

Another important vital factor that directly affects the formation of ecological culture is its close connection with the educational and educational system. Our first president Islam Karimov also points out in his works about education: "of course, education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is the most important factor that also determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it shapes and enriches the spirituality of the people. Consequently, spirituality cannot be developed without changing the educational system and the mind at the base." [1, 61]

Today, young people make up 60% of the population of Uzbekistan. Therefore, in order to educate the future generation environmentally, morally and aesthetically, and further develop their rational attitude towards nature in youth, we should focus 60% of the total activity carried out in our country on youth. In order to achieve our first president's "Great State, great future, we must educate wise, enlightened, at the same time proud of his past, great values, nationality and confident in the future. It is necessary to take as a basis the strict and unique words " [2, 162].

In the spirit of the ecological culture of our youth, we are obliged to cultivate those who always maintain their position on the global level – those who persistently perceive these sacred feelings, so that they perceive their personal interests, harmonious with the interests of el yurt.

If today we are committed to growing our young people as worthy individuals on the path to preserving Mother Nature, our great independence, our distribution will always be in our hands at the world level in the system of global environmental and political relations. It will not be a mistake if I say that this is our supreme goal.

Those who do not have beautiful moral qualities do not have an incentive to study environmental knowledge, to be rational in nature, nor to master a profession that benefits people. Therefore, at all stages of the development of ecological culture, it is from the main tasks of the state to educate and educate the young generation, which is growing above all, morally and aesthetically.

The first president, Islam Karimov, also says: “education cannot be separated from upbringing, and upbringing from education – this is an oriental vision, an oriental philosophy of Life” [1, 62].

Thus, “science is related to ethics, both directly and indirectly, and it is this connection that functions to humanize the natural-technical sciences” [7] that makes a reasonable point in the idea. Therefore, spirituality, formed on the basis of knowledge, science, talent, experience, gives a special direction, opportunity to its moral attitude and activity towards nature.

CONCLUSION

Science has always helped a person in solving difficult and complex tasks. It is with the help of science that most of what once seemed unattainable, beyond the level of human capabilities was achieved. It is for this reason that the first warnings that global problems pose a threat forced the self-centered people to turn their attention to science, and scientists to look for ways to solve these problems.

The peculiarity and novelty of the situation that has arisen is that while any specific problems can be studied within the framework of some science or a set of several disciplines, some disciplines are not capable of researching global

problems consisting of a complex system that covers man, society and nature in their numerous interactions and interactions. Zero is the object of his research – the narrowness of the scope of certain disciplines to interpret this or that problem in the context of other global problems. Therefore, regardless of which specific tasks this or that science solves, a philosophical approach to the processes and phenomena associated with them, that is, to the whole situation, including ultimately the results obtained, is always a prerequisite for research.

Any particular science at a certain stage will need to one degree or another to philosophically understand its subject of research. It is impossible both to make fundamental discoveries and the development of science as a whole without such a broad approach to the subject of a particular science and the problems facing humanity.

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